

Supplementary methods

Chromatography and spectroscopy

Column chromatography was performed using Merck silica gel type 9385 230-400 mesh and typically pentane and ethyl acetate as eluent.

TLC: Merck silica gel 60, 0.25 mm. The components were visualized by UV or KMnO₄ staining.

Gas Chromatography was used for product identification as well as determination of conversion and selectivity values. Product identification was performed by GC-MS (Shimadzu QP2010 Ultra) with an HP-1MS column, and helium as carrier gas. GC-MS method: The temperature program started at 50 °C for 5 min, heated by 30°C/minute to 250 °C and held for 15 min.

Conversions and product selectivities were determined by GC-FID (Agilent Technologies 6890) with an HP-5MS column using nitrogen as carrier gas. GC-FID analysis method: The temperature program started at 50 °C for 5 min, heated by 30°C/min to 320 °C and held for 15 min.

Mass spectrometry: Mass spectra were recorded on an AEI-MS-902 mass spectrometer (EI⁺) or an LTQ Orbitrap XL (ESI⁺).

NMR spectroscopy: ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian Mercury Plus 400, Agilent MR 400 (400 and 101 MHz, respectively), Varian Inova 500 (500 and 126 MHz, respectively) and Bruker Avance NEO 600 (600 and 151 MHz, respectively) using CDCl₃ as a solvent. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded at room temperature. Chemical shift values are reported in ppm with the solvent resonance as the internal standard (CDCl₃: 7.26 for ¹H, 77.00 for ¹³C; Toluene-*d*₈: 7.09, 7.01, 6.97, 2.08 for ¹H, 137.48, 128.87, 127.96, 125.13, 20.43 for ¹³C). Data are reported as follows: chemical shifts, multiplicity (s = singlet, d = doublet, t = triplet, q = quartet, br. = broad, m = multiplet), coupling constants (Hz), and integration.

All reactions were carried out under an Argon atmosphere using oven (120 °C) dried glassware and using standard Schlenk techniques. 1-Hydroxytetraphenylcyclopentadienyl-(tetraphenyl-2,4-cyclopentadien-1-one)- μ -hydrotetracarbonyl diruthenium(II) (Shvo's catalyst, **C1**) was purchased from Strem Chemicals, Inc. 3-(4-Methoxyphenylamino)-but-2-enoic acid ethyl ester (**3''aa**) was synthesized according to the literature procedure.¹ All other reagents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, Acros and TCI in reagent or higher grade and were used as received without further purification.

General procedure for the preparation of β -hydroxyl acid esters

Thionyl chloride (0.022 mol) was added dropwise to a stirred solution of the appropriate β -hydroxyl acid (0.02 mol) in dry EtOH (40 mL) at -30 °C at a rate such that the temperature of the reaction mixture did not rise above -30 °C. When the addition was complete, the solution was stirred at -30 °C for a further 10 min, and then left at room temperature for 4 h. Afterwards, the contents of the flask were poured into a mixture of finely crushed ice (75 g), a saturated aqueous Na₂CO₃ solution (20 mL), and Et₂O (50 mL). The thus prepared mixture was vigorously shaken in a separating funnel, and the organic layer was washed with brine and dried with anhydrous MgSO₄. After removal of the drying agent and evaporation of the solvent *in vacuo*, the resulting crude methyl ester *rac*-**1a-g** was purified by flash column chromatography to provide the pure β -hydroxyl acid ester.²

General procedure for the preparation of β -amino acid esters

An oven-dried 20 mL Schlenk tube, equipped with a stirring bar, was charged with amine (0.5 mmol, 1 equiv.), β -hydroxyl acid ester (1 mmol, 2 equiv.), Shvo's catalyst (0.005 mmol, 1 mol%), diphenyl phosphate (0.025 mmol, 5 mol%) and toluene (as a solvent, 2 mL). Solid materials were weighed into

the Schlenk tube under air. Then the Schlenk tube was subsequently connected to an argon line and vacuum-argon exchange was performed three times. Liquid starting materials and solvent were charged under an argon stream. The Schlenk tube was capped and the mixture was rapidly stirred at room temperature for 1 min, then was placed into a pre-heated oil bath at 120 °C and stirred for a given time (typically, 18 h). Then, the reaction mixture was cooled down to room temperature. After taking a sample (app. 0.5 mL) for GC analysis, the crude mixture was filtered through silica gel, eluted with ethyl acetate, and concentrated *in vacuo*. The residue was purified by flash column chromatography to provide the pure β -amino acid ester product.

General procedure for *in situ* ^{31}P NMR study

An oven-dried 20 mL Schlenk tube, equipped with a stirring bar, was charged (depending on the experiment) with Shvo's catalyst (0.02 mmol, 1 equiv.), diphenyl phosphate (0.02 mmol, 1 equiv.) and/or 3-(4-methoxyphenylamino)-but-2-enoic acid ethyl ester (**3''aa**, 0.02 mmol, 1 equiv.) and toluene- d_8 (as a solvent, 1 mL). Solid materials were weighed into the Schlenk tube under air. Then the Schlenk tube was subsequently connected to an argon line and vacuum-argon exchange was performed three times. Liquid starting materials and solvent were charged under an argon stream. The Schlenk tube was capped and the mixture was rapidly stirred at room temperature for 1 min, then was placed into a pre-heated oil bath (60 °C) and stirred for 15 min. Then, the reaction mixture was cooled down to room temperature. Preparing the sample, 0.6 mL of the reaction mixture was placed to a *J*-Young NMR tube under argon. All spectra were recorded using Bruker Avance NEO 600 machine.

General procedure for the hydrogenation of *N*-aryl enamine (3''aa**)**

An oven-dried 20 mL Schlenk tube, equipped with a stirring bar, was charged with Shvo's catalyst (0.002 mmol, 1 equiv.), diphenyl phosphate (0.01 mmol, 1 equiv.) or 3-(4-methoxyphenylamino)-but-2-enoic acid ethyl ester (**3''aa**, 0.2 mmol, 1 equiv.) and toluene (as a solvent, 2 mL). Solid materials were weighed into the Schlenk tube under air. Then the Schlenk tube was subsequently connected to an argon line and vacuum-argon exchange was performed three times. Liquid starting materials and solvent were charged under an argon stream. The Schlenk tube was capped and the mixture was rapidly stirred at room temperature for 1 minute. At the same time the pre-dried autoclave, equipped with the stirring bar, was purged three times with hydrogen. Under the steam of hydrogen, the reaction mixture was transferred from the Schlenk tube to the autoclave and heated at 90 °C for the 15 minutes. The autoclave was then cooled to RT and the reaction mixture was transferred to a flask. The reaction mixture was analysed by GS-MS and GC-FID to determine conversion of the reaction.

General procedure for deuterium incorporation experiment using **1b-d1 as a substrate**

An oven-dried 20 mL Schlenk tube, equipped with a stirring bar, was charged with Shvo's catalyst (0.001 mmol, 1 mol%), diphenyl phosphate (0.005 mmol, 5 mol%), ethyl 3-hydroxyhexanoate-3-d (**1b-d1**, 0.1 mmol, 1 equiv.), *p*-anisidine (**2a**, 0.1 mmol, 1 equiv.) and toluene- d_8 (as a solvent, 0.6 mL). Solid materials were weighed into the Schlenk tube under air. Then the Schlenk tube was subsequently connected to an argon line and vacuum-argon exchange was performed three times. Liquid starting materials and solvent were charged under an argon stream. The Schlenk tube was capped and the mixture was rapidly stirred at room temperature for 1 min, then was placed into a pre-heated oil bath (120 °C) and stirred for 18 hours. Then, the reaction mixture was cooled down to room temperature. Preparing the sample, 0.6 mL of the reaction mixture was placed to a *J*-Young NMR tube under argon. All spectra were recorded using Varian Mercury Plus 400 machine.

General procedure for deuterium incorporation experiment using benzyl alcohol- α,α - d_2 as a substrate

An oven-dried 20 mL Schlenk tube, equipped with a stirring bar, was charged with Shvo's catalyst (0.001 mmol, 1 mol%), diphenyl phosphate (0.005 mmol, 5 mol%), benzyl alcohol- α,α - d_2 (0.1 mmol, 1 equiv.), aniline (0.1 mmol, 1 equiv.) and toluene- d_8 (as a solvent, 0.6 mL). Solid materials were weighed into the Schlenk tube under air. Then the Schlenk tube was subsequently connected to an argon line and

vacuum-argon exchange was performed three times. Liquid starting materials and solvent were charged under an argon stream. The Schlenk tube was capped and the mixture was rapidly stirred at room temperature for 1 min, then was placed into a pre-heated oil bath (120 °C) and stirred for 18 hours. Then, the reaction mixture was cooled down to room temperature. Preparing the sample, 0.6 mL of the reaction mixture was placed to a J-Young NMR tube under argon. All spectra were recorded using Bruker Avance NEO 600 machine.

General procedure for amination of chiral β -hydroxyl acid esters

An oven-dried 20 mL Schlenk tube, equipped with a stirring bar, was charged with *p*-anisidine (**2a**, 0.5 mmol, 1 equiv.), ethyl (3*R*)-3-hydroxybutanoate (**(R)**-**1a**) or ethyl (3*S*)-3-hydroxybutanoate (**(S)**-**1a**) (1 mmol, 2 equiv.), Shvo's catalyst (0.005 mmol, 1 mol%), diphenyl phosphate (0.025 mmol, 5 mol%) and toluene (as a solvent, 2 mL). Solid materials were weighed into the Schlenk tube under air. Then the Schlenk tube was subsequently connected to an argon line and vacuum-argon exchange was performed three times. Liquid starting materials and solvent were charged under an argon stream. The Schlenk tube was capped and the mixture was rapidly stirred at room temperature for 1 min, then was placed into a pre-heated oil bath at 120 °C and stirred for 18 h. Then, the reaction mixture was cooled down to room temperature; the reaction mixture was analysed by GS-MS and GC-FID to determine conversion and selectivity of the reaction. Enantiomeric excess was determined by chiral HPLC. Conditions: Chiralpak AD-H column, 90:10 heptane:isopropanol, 0.5 mL/min.

Supplementary Figure 1: *In situ* ¹H NMR study of the amination of ethyl 3-hydroxybutanoate (**1a**, 1 mmol) with *p*-anisidine (**2a**, 0.5 mmol) in presence of Shvo's catalyst (**Cat**, 0.005 mmol) and diphenyl phosphate additive (**A1**, 0.025 mmol) in toluene-*d*₈ at 120 °C after 2 hours.

B:{¹H-¹³C}HMBC

C:{¹H-¹³C}HSQC

Supplementary Figure 2: (A) Evidence of ethyl 3-oxobutanoate (1'a) formation according to the ¹³C NMR. **(B)** Evidence for enamine (3''aa) according to {¹H-¹³C}HMBC, **(C)** {¹H-¹³C}HSQC 2D NMR analysis.

Supplementary Figure 3: *In situ* ^1H NMR study of the amination of ethyl 3-hydroxybutanoate (**1a**, 1 mmol) with *p*-anisidine (**2a**, 0.5 mmol) in presence of Shvo's catalyst (**Cat**, 0.005 mmol) **only** in toluene- d_8 at 120 °C after 2 hours.

A: $\{^1\text{H}-^{13}\text{C}\}$ HMBC

B: $\{^1\text{H}-^{13}\text{C}\}$ HSQC

Supplementary Figure 4: Evidence of the ethyl 3-oxobutanoate (**1'a**) formation according to (A) the $\{^1\text{H}-^{13}\text{C}\}$ HMBC and (B) $\{^1\text{H}-^{13}\text{C}\}$ HSQC 2D NMR analysis.

Supplementary Figure 5: (A) ¹H NMR spectrum of the 3-(4-methoxyphenylamino)-but-2-enoic acid ethyl ester (3''aa), which was synthesized according to the literature procedure. **(B)** ¹³C NMR spectrum of the 3-(4-methoxyphenylamino)-but-2-enoic acid ethyl ester (3''aa), which was synthesized according to the literature procedure.

Observed other products of the reaction:

Supplementary Figure 6: Amination of ethyl 3-hydroxy-2,2-dimethylpropanoate (**1e**) with *p*-anisidine (**2a**) in presence of Shvo's catalyst (**Cat**) and diphenyl phosphate additive (**A1**).

Supplementary Figure 7: *In situ* ^1H NMR study of the amination of ethyl 3-hydroxy-2,2-dimethylpropanoate (**1e**, 1 mmol) with *p*-anisidine (**2a**, 0.5 mmol) in presence of Shvo's catalyst (**Cat.**, 0.005 mmol) and diphenyl phosphate additive (**A1**, 0.025 mmol) in toluene- d_8 at 120 °C after 2 hours.

A: $\{^1\text{H}-^{13}\text{C}\}$ HMBC

B: $\{^1\text{H}-^{13}\text{C}\}$ HSQC

Supplementary Figure 8: Evidence of the imine product formation (**3'ea**) according to (A) the $\{^1\text{H}-^{13}\text{C}\}$ HMBC and (B) $\{^1\text{H}-^{13}\text{C}\}$ HSQC 2D NMR analysis.

Supplementary Figure 9: GC-FID chromatogram of the amination of ethyl 3-hydroxy-2,2-dimethylpropanoate (**1e**) with *p*-anisidine (**2a**) in presence of Shvo's catalyst and diphenyl phosphate additive in toluene- d_8 at 120 °C after 2 hours.

Supplementary Figure 10: GC-MS chromatogram of the amination of ethyl 3-hydroxy-2,2-dimethylpropanoate (**1e**) with *p*-anisidine (**2a**) in presence of Shvo's catalyst and diphenyl phosphate additive in toluene- d_8 at 120 °C after 2 hours.

Supplementary Figure 11: Proposed mechanism for the amination of the β -hydroxy acid esters.

Supplementary Figure 12: *In situ* ^{31}P NMR spectra of diphenyl phosphate additive (**A1**), Shvo's complex (**Cat**) and 3-(4-methoxyphenylamino)-but-2-enoic acid ethyl ester (**3''aa**) in different ratios: **a)** diphenyl phosphate (**A1**, -9.45 ppm); **b)** 1:1 mixture of diphenyl phosphate (**A1**) and Shvo's catalyst (**Cat**) (formation of possible **Complex 1** at 1.69 ppm); **c)** 1:1:1 mixture of diphenyl phosphate (**A1**), Shvo's catalyst (**Cat**) and 3-(4-methoxyphenylamino)-but-2-enoic acid ethyl ester (**3''aa**) (formation of possible **Complex 2** at -0.31 ppm and **Adduct 3** at -11.64 ppm); **d)** 1:1 mixture of diphenyl phosphate (**A1**) and 3-(4-methoxyphenylamino)-but-2-enoic acid ethyl ester (**3''aa**) (formation of possible **Adduct 3** at -11.39 ppm).

Supplementary Note 1: Additional description belonging to Supplementary Figure 12

Initially, the spectrum of pure diphenyl phosphate (**A1**) was recorded (**Supplementary Figure 12a**) displaying a typical chemical shift at -9.45 ppm. Next, the mixture of Shvo's complex (**Cat**) and diphenyl phosphate (**A1**) (1:1) at 60 °C after 15 minutes (**Supplementary Figure 12b**) was recorded in order to assess possible interaction between additive and catalyst. Indeed, beside the signal of the free additive (-9.39 ppm) a weak signal at -1.69 ppm appeared, that can be attributed to the formation of adduct between diphenyl phosphate (**A1**) and Shvo's complex (**Cat**) (**Complex 1**). Interestingly, when to the mixture of Shvo's complex (**Cat**) and diphenyl phosphate (**A1**) (1:1) the enamine 3-(4-methoxyphenylamino)-but-2-enoic acid ethyl ester (**3''aa**) was added (obtained separately by synthetic procedures), the signal was shifted to -0.31 ppm that can be explained by the formation of the corresponding adduct between **A1**, **Cat** and **3''aa** (**Supplementary Figure 12c**, **Complex 2**). Analogous interactions between metal complexes and Brønsted acid additives (as **Complex 2** in our case) were reported by Beller using Knölker iron complex and chiral Brønsted acid (3,3'-bis(2,4,6-triisopropylphenyl)-1,1'-binaphthyl-2,2'-diyl hydrogen phosphate (*S*)-TRIP) for the hydrogenation of imines^{3,4} and by Gandon using Vaska's complex with chiral phosphate additive for the enantioselective carbocyclization of 1,6-enynes.⁵ Herein **Complex 2** is displayed as the more stable, amine-coordinated species, which is proposed to form upon interaction of **3''aa** and **A1** with the 'reducing' half of Shvo's complex as depicted below.

In spectrum **Supplementary Figure 12c**, the chemical shift at -11.64 ppm can be attributed to **Adduct 3**, between **A1** and **3'**. This has been additionally confirmed by separately recording the spectrum of readily prepared **3''** and **A1** without the catalyst, displaying a shift at -11.39 ppm (**Supplementary Figure 12d**). Rueping observed a very similar chemical shift (singlet at approximately -13 ppm in ³¹P NMR spectrum) related to the formation of intermolecular hydrogen bonded species between diphenyl phosphate and (*E*)-*N*-phenyl-1-(*p*-tolyl) methanimine, comparable to **Adduct 3** in our case.⁶ It has to be noted, that we display here **Adduct 3** as a hydrogen bonded species. In their work Rueping detected the hydrogen bonded as well as the corresponding ionic species by low temperatures ¹H NMR, with only one ³¹P NMR signal observed around -13 ppm.

We assume that in the presence of **A1** the equilibrium is shifted to the imine **3''aa** formed during the borrowing hydrogen cycle while in the absence of additive tautomerization to the corresponding enamine **3''aa** would take place. Via **Complex 2**, **3''aa** is readily reduced to the desired β -amino acid ester (**3**).

Supplementary Note 2: Deuterium incorporation experiments

Supplementary Figure 13: Deuterium incorporation experiment using **1b-d1** as a substrate.

Using other simple model substrates:

In presence of **Cat** (1 mol%), **A1** (5 mol%): conversion – 98%; selectivity – 91% (determined by GC-FID).

In presence of **Cat** (1 mol%) only: conversion – 38%; selectivity – 17% (determined by GC-FID).

Supplementary Figure 14: Deuterium incorporation experiment using benzyl alcohol- α,α -d₂ as a substrate.

Supplementary Note 3: Amination reactions with chiral alcohols

The amination of chiral alcohols, namely ethyl (*S*)-3-hydroxybutyrate (**(S)-1a**) and ethyl (*R*)-3-hydroxybutyrate (**(R)-1a**) with *p*-anisidine (**2a**) delivered the desired β -amino acid esters with complete loss of chiral information, which confirmed the proposed hydrogen borrowing mechanism.

(a)

Supplementary Figure 15: HPLC trace of racemic (a) and (**R**)-3aa (b).

Supplementary Figure 16: HPLC trace of racemic (a) and (**S**)-3aa (b).

Supplementary Table 1: Scope of the reaction with the respect to variation of the amine.

Entry	Amine (2)	Product (3)	Conv. [%]	Sel. [%]
1	2a 	3aa	>99	>99(87)
2	2b 	3ab	>99	77(58)
3	2c 	3ac	>99	76(58)
4	2d 	3ad	>99	61(48)
5	2e 	3ae	95	77(59)
6	2f 	3af	>99	75(56)
7	2g 	3ag	>99	73(47)
8	2h 	3ah	>99	81(76)
9	2i 	3ai	>99	>99(79)
10	2j 	3aj	>99	88(87)
11	2k 	3ak	>99	86(70)
12	2l 	3al	>99	85(63)
13	2m 	3am	>99	66(37)
14	2n 	3an	>99	84(70)
15	2o 	3ao	>99	77(46)
16	2p 	3ap	>99	83(78)

17	2q		3aq	94	78(56)
18	2r		3ar	>99	58(44)

General reaction conditions: General Procedure, 1 mmol of **1a**, 0.5 mmol of **2a-r**, 1 mol% Shvo's complex (**Cat**), 5 mol% additive (**A1**), 2 mL toluene, 18 hours, 120 °C, under argon, isolated yields in parentheses. Conversion and selectivity were determined by GC-FID.

Supplementary Table 2: Scope of the reaction with the respect to variation of β -hydroxyl acid ester substrate.

Entry	1a-f	R = OCH ₃ (2a), Br (2i)		R = OCH ₃ (3aa-3fa), Br (3ai-3fi)	
		Alcohol (1)	Product (3)	Conv. [%]	Sel. [%]
1	1a		3aa	>99	>99(87)
2	1a		3ai	>99	>99(79)
3	1b		3ba	>99	>99(79)
4	1b		3bi	>99	92(68)
5	1c		3ca	>99	82(78)
6	1c		3ci	>99	77(54)
7	1d		3da	>99	73(43)
8	1d		3di	>99	72(48)
9	1e		3ea	>99	>99(81)
10	1e		3ei	>99	>99(96)
11	1f		3fa	79	69(33) ^a
12	1f		3fi	83	83(59)

General reaction conditions: General Procedure, 1 mmol of **1a-f**, 0.5 mmol of **2a** or **2i**, 1 mol% Shvo's complex (**Cat**), 5 mol% additive (**A1**), 2 mL toluene, 18 hours, 120 °C, under argon, isolated yields in parentheses. Conversion and selectivity were determined by GC-FID. ^a 48 h.

Supplementary Table 3: Scope of the reaction for the synthesis of bio-based β -amino acid esters via direct catalytic amination of *tert*-butyl 3-hydroxypropionate (**1i**) and ethyl-3-hydroxypropanoate (**1j**).

Entry	β -hydroxyl acid ester (1)	Amine (2)	Product (3)	Conv. [%]	Sel. [%]
1		2a	3ia	91	77(52) ^a
2		2a	3ia [^]	>99	72(51) ^b
3		2i	3ii	>99	85(52)
4		2k	3ik	>99	84(72)
5		2m	3im	>99	79(59)
6		2o	3io	95	85(48)
7 ^c		2a	3ia	50	44
8		2a	3ja	90	73(49)
9		2a	3ja [^]	>99	69(56)
10		2i	3ji	>99	64(55)
11		2k	3jk	89	60(45)
12		2m	3jm	78	54(51)

General reaction conditions: 1 mmol of **1i-j**, 0.5 mmol of **2a-o**, 1 mol% Shvo's complex (**Cat**), 5 mol% additive (**A1**), 2 mL toluene, 18 hours, 120 °C, under argon, isolated yields in parentheses. Conversion and selectivity were determined by GC-FID. ^a 48 h. ^b Used 2 mol% of **Cat** and 5 mol% of **A1**, 48 h. ^c Without 5 mol% of **A1**.

Supplementary Note 4

Ethyl 3-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)butanoate (**3aa**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-methoxyaniline (61.5 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxybutanoate (132 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3aa** (103 mg, 87% yield). Yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 90:10). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 6.77 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.60 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.13 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 3.84 (sext, *J* = 5.6 Hz, 1H), 3.73 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.35 (*br s*, 1H), 2.59 (dd, *J* = 14.8 Hz, *J* = 5.6 Hz, 1H), 2.38 (dd, *J* = 14.8 Hz, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 1.26-1.23 (m, 6H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 174.58, 155.04, 143.63, 118.09, 117.58, 63.05, 58.36, 49.89, 43.65, 23.27, 16.87. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₃H₂₀NO₃ [M+H]⁺: 238.14432; found: 238.14403. The spectral data are identical to the previously reported.⁷

Ethyl 3-((4-phenoxyphenyl)amino)butanoate (**3ab**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-phenoxyaniline (93 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxybutanoate (132 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3ab** (87 mg, 58% yield). Light yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.30-7.26 (m, 2H), 7.01 (t, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 6.96-6.90 (m, 4H), 6.64 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.16 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 3.92 (sext, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 1H), 3.68 (*br s*, 1H), 2.64 (dd, *J* = 15.2 Hz, *J* = 5.6 Hz, 1H), 2.45 (dd, *J* = 15.2 Hz, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 1.30-1.25 (m, 6H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 174.48, 161.65, 150.58, 146.08, 132.16, 124.65, 123.90, 119.84, 117.46, 63.16, 49.37, 43.67, 23.29, 16.91. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₈H₂₂NO₃ [M+H]⁺: 300.15997; found: 300.16013.

Ethyl 3-((3,5-dimethoxyphenyl)amino)butanoate (**3ac**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 3,5-dimethoxyaniline (76.5 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxybutanoate (132 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3ac** (78 mg, 58% yield). Light yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 90:10). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 5.88-5.87 (m, 1H), 5.82-5.80 (m, 2H), 4.13 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 3.89 (sext, *J* = 5.6 Hz, 2H), 3.73 (s, 6H), 2.62 (dd, *J* = 14.8 Hz, *J* = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 2.41 (dd, *J* = 15.2 Hz, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 1.26-1.23 (m, 6H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 174.40, 164.42, 151.39, 94.95, 92.63, 63.11, 57.76, 48.65, 43.61, 23.19, 16.86. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₄H₂₂NO₄ [M+H]⁺: 268.15488; found: 268.15501.

Ethyl 3-((3,4,5-trimethoxyphenyl)amino)butanoate (3ad)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 3,4,5-trimethoxyaniline (91.5 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxybutanoate (132 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3ad** (72 mg, 48% yield). Light yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 90:10 to 80:20). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 5.85 (s, 2H), 4.12 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 3.90-3.81 (m, 1H), 3.79 (s, 6H), 3.73 (s, 3H), 2.60 (dd, *J* = 14.8 Hz, *J* = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 2.39 (dd, *J* = 14.8 Hz, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 1.26-1.21 (m, 6H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 174.51, 156.62, 146.21, 132.89, 93.95, 63.67, 63.13, 58.56, 49.27, 43.74, 23.31, 16.85. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₅H₂₄NO₅ [M+H]⁺: 298.16545; found: 298.16533.

Ethyl 3-([1,1'-biphenyl]-4-ylamino)butanoate (3ae)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-aminobiphenyl (84.5 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxybutanoate (132 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3ae** (83 mg, 59% yield). Light yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.58 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 7.48 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 7.43 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 7.31-7.27 (m, 1H), 6.73 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.19 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 4.03 (sext, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 1H), 3.93 (*br s*, 1H), 2.68 (dd, *J* = 14.8 Hz, *J* = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 2.48 (dd, *J* = 14.8 Hz, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 1.34 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 3H), 1.30 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 174.47, 148.97, 143.86, 133.18, 131.34, 130.70, 128.96, 128.77, 116.48, 63.21, 48.75, 43.73, 23.33, 16.93. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₈H₂₂NO₂[M+H]⁺: 284.16505; found: 284.16462.

Ethyl 3-((4-(*tert*-butyl)phenyl)amino)butanoate (3af)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-(*tert*-butyl)aniline (74.5 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxybutanoate (132 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3af** (74 mg, 56% yield). Light yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.22 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.60 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.15 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 3.94 (sext, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 1H), 3.69 (*br s*, 1H), 2.65 (dd, *J* = 14.8 Hz, *J* = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 2.41 (dd, *J* = 14.8 Hz, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 1H), 1.30-1.25 (m, 15H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 174.56, 147.07, 143.05, 128.75, 115.98, 63.08, 48.90, 43.86, 36.51, 34.21, 23.42, 16.90. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₆H₂₆NO₂ [M+H]⁺: 264.19635; found: 264.19620.

Ethyl 3-((4-fluorophenyl)amino)butanoate (3ag)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-fluoroaniline (56 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxybutanoate (132 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3ag** (53 mg, 47% yield). Light yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 6.90-6.85 (m, 2H), 6.56 (dd, *J* = 9.2 Hz, *J* = 4.8 Hz, 2H), 4.13 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 3.85 (sext, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 1H), 3.61 (*br s*, 1H), 2.58 (dd, *J* = 14.8 Hz, *J* = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 2.41 (dd, *J* = 14.8 Hz, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 1H), 1.26-1.23 (m, 6H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 174.43, 158.59 (d, *J*_{CF} = 236.3 Hz), 145.83, 118.38 (d, *J*_{CF} = 22.2 Hz), 117.36 (d, *J*_{CF} = 7.1 Hz), 63.14, 49.53, 43.55, 23.18, 16.85. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₂H₁₇FNO₂ [M+H]⁺: 226.12433; found: 226.12396. The spectral data are identical to the previously reported.⁸

Ethyl 3-((4-chlorophenyl)amino)butanoate (3ah)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-chloroaniline (64 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxybutanoate (132 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3ah** (92 mg, 76% yield). Light yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.10 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.53 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.13 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 3.88 (sext, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 1H), 3.81 (*br s*, 1H), 2.58 (dd, *J* = 15.2 Hz, *J* = 5.6 Hz, 1H), 2.42 (dd, *J* = 14.8 Hz, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 1H), 1.26-1.23 (m, 6H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 174.31, 148.08, 131.79, 124.77, 117.31, 63.20, 48.87, 43.48, 23.11, 16.86. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₂H₁₇ClNO₂ [M+H]⁺: 242.09478; found: 242.09475. The spectral data are identical to the previously reported.⁹

Ethyl 3-((4-bromophenyl)amino)butanoate (3ai)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-bromoaniline (86 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxybutanoate (132 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3ai** (112 mg, 79% yield). Light yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.24 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.49 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.13 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 3.88 (sext, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 1H), 2.57 (dd, *J* = 14.8 Hz, *J* = 5.6 Hz, 1H), 2.43 (dd, *J* = 14.8 Hz, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 1H), 1.26-1.23 (m, 6H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 174.29, 148.52, 134.67, 117.76, 111.76, 63.21, 48.75, 43.46, 23.10, 16.87. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₂H₁₇BrNO₂ [M+H]⁺: 286.04427; found: 286.04430. The spectral data are identical to the previously reported.⁷

Ethyl 3-((4-bromo-3-methylphenyl)amino)butanoate (**3aj**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-bromo-3-methylaniline (93 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxybutanoate (132 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3aj** (130 mg, 87% yield). Light yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.26 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 1H), 6.50 (d, *J* = 2.8 Hz, 1H), 6.34 (dd, *J* = 8.8 Hz, *J* = 2.8 Hz, 1H), 4.14 (q, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 2H), 3.88 (sext, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 1H), 3.78 (*br s*, 1H), 2.58 (dd, *J* = 15.2 Hz, *J* = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 2.42 (dd, *J* = 14.8 Hz, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 1H), 2.30 (s, 3H), 1.27-1.23 (m, 6H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 174.34, 148.82, 140.98, 135.38, 118.60, 115.33, 114.56, 63.18, 48.75, 43.53, 25.72, 23.15, 16.88. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₃H₁₉BrNO₂ [M+H]⁺: 300.05992; found: 300.06026.

Ethyl 3-((4-bromo-3-fluorophenyl)amino)butanoate (**3ak**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-bromo-3-fluoroaniline (95 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxybutanoate (132 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3ak** (107 mg, 70% yield). Light yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.22 (t, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 6.37 (dd, *J* = 11.2 Hz, *J* = 2.8 Hz, 1H), 6.27 (dd, *J* = 8.4 Hz, *J* = 2.4 Hz, 1H), 4.13 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 4.05 (*br s*, 1H), 3.84 (sext, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 1H), 2.56 (dd, *J* = 15.2 Hz, *J* = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 2.44 (dd, *J* = 15.2 Hz, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 1.26-1.22 (m, 6H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 174.12, 162.49 (d, *J*_{CF} = 244.9 Hz), 150.56 (d, *J*_{CF} = 9.1 Hz), 136.04, 113.27 (d, *J*_{CF} = 2.5 Hz), 103.69 (d, *J*_{CF} = 26.2 Hz), 97.36 (d, *J*_{CF} = 21.6 Hz), 63.30, 48.72, 43.34, 22.96, 16.84. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₂H₁₆BrFNO₂ [M+H]⁺: 304.03484; found: 304.03449.

Ethyl 3-((4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)amino)butanoate (**3al**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-(trifluoromethyl)aniline (81 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxybutanoate (132 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3al** (86 mg, 63% yield). Light yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.39 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 2H), 6.61 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.21 (*br s*, 1H, NH), 4.15 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 3.97 (sext, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 1H), 2.60 (dd, *J* = 15.2 Hz, *J* = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 2.47 (dd, *J* = 15.2 Hz, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 1.29 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 3H), 1.25 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 171.51, 149.39, 126.68, 124.94 (q, *J* = 716.4 Hz), 118.94 (q, *J* = 32.62 Hz), 112.40, 60.65, 45.64, 40.80, 20.39, 14.16. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₃H₁₇F₃NO₂ [M+H]⁺: 276.12114; found: 276.12100.

Ethyl 3-((4-nitrophenyl)amino)butanoate (**3am**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-nitroaniline (69 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxybutanoate (132 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3am** (47 mg, 37% yield). Bright yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 90:10 to 80:20). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 8.06 (d, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 2H), 6.54 (d, *J* = 9.6 Hz, 2H), 4.88 (*br s*, 1H, NH), 4.14 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 4.03 (sext, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 1H), 2.60 (dd, *J* = 15.2 Hz, *J* = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 2.52 (dd, *J* = 15.2 Hz, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 1H), 1.32 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 3H), 1.24 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 173.87, 154.77, 140.64, 129.13, 114.09, 63.49, 48.30, 43.22, 22.90, 16.82. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₂H₁₇N₂O₄ [M+H]⁺: 253.11883; found: 253.11823.

Methyl 4-((4-ethoxy-4-oxobutan-2-yl)amino)benzoate (**3an**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using methyl 4-aminobenzoate (75.5 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxybutanoate (132 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3an** (93 mg, 70% yield). Colorless oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 90:10). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.83 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.54 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.40 (*br s*, 1H), 4.12 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 4.01-3.97 (m, 1H), 3.82 (s, 3H), 2.59 (dd, *J* = 15.2 Hz, *J* = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 2.44 (dd, *J* = 14.8 Hz, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 1H), 1.27 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 3H), 1.22 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 174.10, 169.87, 153.32, 134.25, 121.08, 114.59, 63.28, 54.15, 48.11, 43.48, 23.06, 16.82. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₄H₂₀NO₄ [M+H]⁺: 266.13923; found: 266.13895.

Ethyl 3-((4-cyanophenyl)amino)butanoate (**3ao**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-aminobenzonitrile (59 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxybutanoate (132 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3ao** (54 mg, 46% yield). Light yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 90:10). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.39 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.56 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.53 (*br s*, 1H), 4.12 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 4.01-3.90 (m, 1H), 2.57 (dd, *J* = 15.2 Hz, *J* = 5.6 Hz, 1H), 2.46 (dd, *J* = 15.2 Hz, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 1.28 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 3H), 1.22 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 170.30, 149.04, 132.79, 119.32, 111.64, 97.90, 59.75, 44.41, 39.66, 19.31, 13.17. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₃H₁₇N₂O₂ [M+H]⁺: 233.12900; found: 233.12848.

Ethyl 3-((2,3-dihydrobenzo[b][1,4]dioxin-6-yl)amino)butanoate (3ap)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 1,4-benzodioxan-6-amine (76 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxybutanoate (132 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3ap** (103 mg, 78% yield). Yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5 to 90:10). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 6.67 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 1H), 6.18-6.13 (m, 2H), 4.20-4.09 (m, 6H), 3.79 (sext, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 1H), 3.40 (*br s*, 1H), 2.57 (dd, *J* = 15.2 Hz, *J* = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 2.37 (dd, *J* = 14.8 Hz, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 1.25-1.20(m, 6H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 174.47, 146.71, 144.39, 138.54, 120.31, 110.45, 105.36, 67.35, 66.81, 63.04, 49.58, 43.59, 23.20, 16.87. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₄H₂₀NO₄ [M+H]⁺: 266.13923; found: 266.13934.

Ethyl 3-(pyren-1-ylamino)butanoate (3aq)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 1-aminopyrene (109.5 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxybutanoate (132 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3aq** (110 mg, 56% yield). Bright yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 8.09-7.81 (m, 8H), 7.42-7.40 (m, 1H), 5.17 (*br s*, 1H), 4.39-4.30 (m, 1H), 4.23 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 2.82 (dd, *J* = 15.2 Hz, *J* = 5.2 Hz, 1H), 2.68 (dd, *J* = 15.2 Hz, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 1H), 1.49 (d, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 3H), 1.30 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 172.02, 141.21, 132.44, 131.74, 127.75, 126.43, 126.24, 125.97, 125.75, 123.93, 123.45, 123.34, 119.61, 117.17, 109.93, 60.74, 46.56, 40.99, 20.64, 14.32. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₂₂H₂₂NO₂[M+H]⁺: 332.16505; found: 332.16320.

Ethyl 3-((2-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)phenyl)amino)butanoate (3ar)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 2-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)aniline (79 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxybutanoate (132 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3ar** (60 mg, 44% yield). Light yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.26 (td, *J* = 6.4 Hz, *J* = 1.6 Hz, 1H), 7.14 (dd, *J* = 7.6 Hz, *J* = 1.6 Hz, 1H), 6.81 (dd, *J* = 8.0 Hz, *J* = 1.2 Hz, 1H), 6.79-6.78 (m, 2H), 6.74 (td, *J* = 7.2 Hz, *J* = 1.2 Hz, 1H), 6.36-6.35 (m, 2H), 4.12 (q, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 2H), 3.97 (sext, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 1H), 3.84 (*br s*, 1H), 2.57 (dd, *J* = 14.8 Hz, *J* = 5.6 Hz, 1H), 2.36 (dd, *J* = 14.8 Hz, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 1H), 1.25-1.20 (m, 6H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 174.09, 145.08, 131.61, 130.29, 130.06, 124.51, 119.42, 114.61, 112.10, 63.19, 48.46, 43.89, 23.23, 16.86. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₆H₂₁N₂O₂ [M+H]⁺: 273.16030; found: 273.15992.

Ethyl 3-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)hexanoate (**3ba**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-methoxyaniline (61.5 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxyhexanoate (160 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3ba** (104 mg, 79% yield). Yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 90:10). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 6.76 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.60 (d, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 2H), 4.11 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 3.73 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.71 (p, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 1H), 2.51 (dd, *J* = 14.8 Hz, *J* = 5.6 Hz, 1H), 2.45 (dd, *J* = 14.8 Hz, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 1H), 1.56-1.34 (m, 4H), 1.23 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H), 0.92 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 174.76, 154.84, 144.10, 117.76, 117.58, 63.00, 58.39, 54.08, 41.95, 39.95, 22.01, 16.86, 16.65. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₅H₂₄NO₃ [M+H]⁺: 266.17562; found: 266.17539.

Ethyl 3-((4-bromophenyl)amino)hexanoate (**3bi**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-bromoaniline (86 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxyhexanoate (160 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3bi** (106 mg, 68% yield). Light yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.22 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.49 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.11 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 3.77-3.72 (m, 2H), 2.54-2.44 (m, 2H), 1.57-1.21 (m, 4H), 1.22 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H), 0.91 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 174.46, 149.00, 134.64, 117.56, 111.45, 63.17, 52.96, 41.91, 39.88, 21.99, 16.85, 16.61. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₄H₂₁BrNO₂ [M+H]⁺: 314.07557; found: 314.07532.

Ethyl 3-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)tetradecanoate (**3ca**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-methoxyaniline (61.5 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxytetradecanoate (272 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3ca** (147 mg, 78% yield). Light yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 98:2). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 6.77 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.60 (d, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 2H), 4.11 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 3.73 (s, 3H), 3.69 (p, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 1H), 3.47 (*br s*, NH, 1H), 2.52 (dd, *J* = 15.2 Hz, *J* = 5.6 Hz, 1H), 2.45 (dd, *J* = 15.2 Hz, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 1H), 1.57-1.22 (m, 23H), 0.88 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 174.76, 154.86, 144.07, 117.80, 117.58, 63.00, 58.39, 54.37, 41.92, 37.73, 34.57, 32.29, 32.27, 32.23, 32.21, 32.19, 32.00, 28.80, 25.34, 16.86, 16.77. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₂₃H₄₀NO₃ [M+H]⁺: 378.30082; found: 378.30132.

Ethyl 3-((4-bromophenyl)amino)tetradecanoate (**3ci**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-bromoaniline (86 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxytetradecanoate (272 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3ci** (116 mg, 54% yield). Light white oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 98:2). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.22 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.49 (d, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 2H), 4.11 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 3.80-3.70 (m, 2H), 2.54-2.44 (m, 2H), 1.56- 1.21 (m, 23H), 0.88 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 174.46, 148.96, 134.64, 117.58, 111.49, 63.15, 53.24, 41.87, 37.66, 34.57, 32.28, 32.27, 32.21, 32.16, 32.14, 31.99, 28.75, 25.34, 16.85, 16.78. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₂₂H₃₇BrNO₂[M+H]⁺: 426.20077; found: 426.20103.

Ethyl 3-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)-3-phenylpropanoate (**3da**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-methoxyaniline (61.5 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxy-3-phenylpropanoate (194 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3da** (84 mg, 48% yield). Yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5 to 90:10). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.38-7.22 (m, 5H), 6.70 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.53 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.78-4.74 (m, 1H), 4.11 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 3.70 (s, 3H), 2.79 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 2H), 1.20 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 173.89, 154.95, 145.10, 143.66, 131.36, 130.02, 128.97, 117.81, 117.40, 63.38, 58.61, 58.34, 45.60, 16.80. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₈H₂₂NO₃ [M+H]⁺: 300.15997; found: 300.15973. The spectral data are identical to the previously reported.¹⁰

Ethyl 3-((4-bromophenyl)amino)-3-phenylpropanoate (**3di**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-bromoaniline (86 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxy-3-phenylpropanoate (194 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3di** (65 mg, 43% yield). Yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5 to 90:10). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.37-7.24 (m, 5H), 7.18 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.44 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.81-4.77 (m, 1H), 4.69 (*br s*, 1H), 4.12 (q, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 2H), 2.85-2.75 (m, 2H), 1.20 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 173.68, 148.48, 144.28, 134.50, 131.50, 130.26, 128.84, 117.94, 112.11, 63.53, 57.66, 45.44, 16.81. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₇H₁₉BrNO₂ [M+H]⁺: 348.05992; found: 348.05995.

Ethyl 3-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)-2,2-dimethylpropanoate (3ea)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-methoxyaniline (61.5 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxy-2,2-dimethylpropanoate (146 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3ea** (101 mg, 81% yield). Light orange oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 90:10). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 6.77 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.60 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.13 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 3.73 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.18 (s, 2H), 1.27 (s, 6H), 1.24 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 179.68, 154.72, 145.53, 117.49, 116.98, 63.29, 58.45, 56.64, 46.15, 26.21, 16.82. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₄H₂₂NO₃[M+H]⁺: 252.15997; found: 252.16005.

Ethyl 3-((4-bromophenyl)amino)-2,2-dimethylpropanoate (3ei)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-bromoaniline (86 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxy-2,2-dimethylpropanoate (146 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3ei** (143 mg, 96% yield). Colorless oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5 to 90:10). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.21 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.49 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.12 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 4.04 (*br s*, 1H, NH), 3.18 (s, 2H), 1.24 (m, 9H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 179.50, 150.19, 134.47, 117.09, 111.29, 63.42, 55.20, 46.19, 26.15, 16.82. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₃H₁₉BrNO₂[M+H]⁺: 300.05992; found: 300.05953.

Ethyl 3-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)-2-phenylpropanoate (3fa)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-methoxyaniline (61.5 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxy-2-phenylpropanoate (194 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **3fa** (49 mg, 33% yield). Yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 90:10). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.38-7.28 (m, 5H), 6.79 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.58 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.21-4.08 (m, 2H), 3.93-3.89 (m, 1H), 3.82-3.75 (m, 4H), 3.42 (dd, *J* = 13.2 Hz, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 1H), 1.20 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 175.55, 155.06, 144.09, 139.57, 131.52, 130.69, 130.28, 117.62, 117.29, 63.64, 58.44, 53.59, 50.62, 16.74. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₈H₂₂NO₃ [M+H]⁺: 300.15997; found: 300.16017. The spectral data are identical to the previously reported.¹¹

Ethyl 3-((4-bromophenyl)amino)-2-phenylpropanoate (**3fi**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-bromoaniline (86 mg, 0.5 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxy-2-phenylpropanoate (194 mg, 1mmol) to afford **3fi** (103 mg, 59% yield). Light yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.38-7.24 (m, 7H), 6.48 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.20-4.10 (m, 2H), 3.91-3.87 (m, 1H), 3.82-3.77 (m, 1H), 3.43 (dd, *J* = 13.6 Hz, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 1H), 1.20 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 175.36, 148.98, 139.24, 134.70, 131.61, 130.63, 130.44, 117.28, 111.98, 63.79, 53.40, 49.44, 16.74. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₇H₁₉BrNO₂ [M+H]⁺: 348.05992; found: 348.05973.

1-(4-bromophenyl)-3,3-dimethylazetidin-2-one (**4ei**)

The compound was synthesized according to the literature procedure¹² using ethyl 3-((4-bromophenyl)amino)-2,2-dimethylpropanoate (300 mg, 1 mmol) and methylmagnesium bromide solution (119 mg, 1 mmol) to afford **4ei** (193 mg, 76% yield). Light yellow solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 95:5). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.35 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.17 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 3.35 (s, 2H), 1.34 (s, 6H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 173.60, 140.27, 134.65, 120.53, 118.67, 55.88, 52.89, 24.02. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₁H₁₃BrNO [M+H]⁺: 254.01805; found: 254.01743.

tert-Butyl 3-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)propanoate (**3ia**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-methoxyaniline (61.5 mg, 0.5 mmol) and *tert*-butyl 3-hydroxypropanoate (146 mg, 1mmol) to afford **3ia** (22 mg, 18% yield). Light yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 90:10). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 6.78 (d, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 2H), 6.62 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 3.75 (s, 3H), 3.35 (t, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 2.51 (t, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 1.45 (s, 9H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 171.95, 152.64, 141.81, 115.04, 114.97, 80.98, 55.92, 41.08, 35.16, 28.26. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₄H₂₂NO₃ [M+H]⁺: 252.15942; found: 252.15926.

Di-*tert*-butyl 3,3'-((4-methoxyphenyl)azanediyl)dipropionate (**3ia[^]**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-methoxyaniline (61.5 mg, 0.5 mmol) and *tert*-butyl 3-hydroxypropanoate (146 mg, 1mmol) to afford **3ia[^]** (97 mg, 51% yield). Colorless oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 90:10). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 6.82 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.72 (d, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 2H), 3.74 (s, 3H), 3.49 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 4H), 2.43 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 4H), 1.43 (s, 18H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 171.66, 152.42, 141.87, 116.12, 114.94, 80.58, 55.77, 48.04, 33.89, 28.17. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₂₁H₃₄NO₅ [M+H]⁺: 380.24315; found: 380.24282.

tert-Butyl 3-((4-bromophenyl)amino)propanoate (**3ii**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-bromoaniline (86 mg, 0.5 mmol) and *tert*-butyl 3-hydroxypropanoate (146 mg, 1mmol) to afford **3ii** (78 mg, 52% yield). Light yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 98:2). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.25 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.51 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 3.36 (t, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 2H), 2.51 (t, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 1.45 (s, 9H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 171.71, 146.73, 132.11, 114.88, 109.49, 81.18, 39.89, 34.92, 28.24. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₃H₁₉BrNO₂ [M+H]⁺: 300.05937; found: 300.05966.

tert-Butyl 3-((4-bromo-3-fluorophenyl)amino)propanoate (**3ik**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-bromo-3-fluoroaniline (95 mg, 0.5 mmol) and *tert*-butyl 3-hydroxypropanoate (146 mg, 1mmol) to afford **3ik** (114 mg, 72% yield). Light yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 98:2). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.27-7.23 (m, 1H), 6.40 (dd, *J* = 11.2 Hz, *J* = 2.4 Hz, 1H), 6.31 (dd, *J* = 8.4 Hz, *J* = 2.0 Hz, 1H), 3.35 (t, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 2.52 (t, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 2H), 1.45 (s, 9H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 171.57, 160.79, 159.17, 148.68, 148.61, 133.55, 133.53, 110.62, 101.09, 100.92, 95.41, 95.27, 81.37, 77.37, 77.16, 76.95, 39.86, 34.74, 28.24. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₃H₁₈BrFNO₂ [M+H]⁺: 318.04995; found: 318.01567.

***tert*-Butyl 3-((4-nitrophenyl)amino)propanoate (3im)**

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-nitroaniline (69 mg, 0.5 mmol) and *tert*-butyl 3-hydroxypropanoate (146 mg, 1mmol) to afford **3im** (78 mg, 59% yield). Bright yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 80:20). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 8.06 (d, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 2H), 6.54 (d, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 2H), 3.48 (t, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 2.55 (t, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 1.44 (s, 9H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 171.29, 153.07, 138.22, 126.53, 111.27, 81.59, 39.10, 34.74, 28.19. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₃H₁₉N₂O₄ [M+H]⁺: 267.13393; found: 267.13373.

***tert*-Butyl 3-((4-cyanophenyl)amino)propanoate (3io)**

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-aminobenzonitrile (59 mg, 0.5 mmol) and *tert*-butyl 3-hydroxypropanoate (146 mg, 1mmol) to afford **3io** (59 mg, 48% yield). Light yellow solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 80:20). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.41 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.57 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 3.43 (t, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 2.53 (t, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 1.44 (s, 9H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 171.39, 150.95, 133.86, 120.45, 112.52, 99.18, 81.47, 39.01, 34.78, 28.21. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₄H₁₉N₂O₂ [M+H]⁺: 247.14410; found: 247.14387. The spectral data are identical to the previously reported.¹³

Ethyl 3-((4-methoxyphenyl)amino)propanoate (3ja)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using *p*-anisidine (37 mg, 0.3 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxypropanoate (71 mg, 0.6 mmol) to afford **3ja** (33 mg, 49% yield). Light yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 90:10). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 6.79 (d, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 2H), 6.62 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.15 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 3.75 (s, 3H), 3.40 (t, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 2.60 (t, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 1.26 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 172.58, 152.62, 141.75, 115.06, 114.85, 60.73, 55.91, 40.79, 34.07, 14.34. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₂H₁₈NO₃ [M+H]⁺: 224.12812; found: 224.12810.

Diethyl 3,3'-((4-methoxyphenyl)azanediyl)dipropionate (**3ja**[^])

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using *p*-anisidine (37 mg, 0.3 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxypropanoate (71 mg, 0.6 mmol) to afford **3ja**[^] (54 mg, 56% yield). Light yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 90:10). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 6.83 (d, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 2H), 6.74 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.11 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 4H), 3.75 (s, 3H), 3.53 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 4H), 2.51 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 4H), 1.24 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 6H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 172.35, 152.72, 141.67, 116.49, 115.00, 60.61, 55.82, 48.18, 32.79, 14.32. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₇H₂₆NO₅ [M+H]⁺: 324.18055; found: 324.18050.

Ethyl 3-((4-bromophenyl)amino)propanoate (**3ji**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-bromoaniline (51 mg, 0.3 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxypropanoate (71 mg, 0.6 mmol) to afford **3ji** (45 mg, 55% yield). Light yellow oil was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 90:10). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.24 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.49 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.15 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 3.40 (t, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 2.59 (t, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 1.26 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (101 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 172.35, 146.73, 132.09, 114.71, 109.37, 60.83, 39.55, 33.84, 14.31. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₁H₁₅BrNO₂ [M+H]⁺: 272.02602; found: 272.02581.

Ethyl 3-((4-bromo-3-fluorophenyl)amino)propanoate (**3jk**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-bromo-3-fluoroaniline (57 mg, 0.3 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxypropanoate (71 mg, 0.6 mmol) to afford **3jk** (39 mg, 45% yield). Light yellow solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 90:10). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.24 (t, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 1H), 6.37 (dd, *J* = 11.2 Hz, *J* = 2.8 Hz, 1H), 6.28 (dd, *J* = 8.8 Hz, *J* = 2.4 Hz, 1H), 4.16 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 3.39 (t, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 2H), 2.59 (t, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 1.26 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 172.25, 159.98 (d, *J*_{CF} = 244.2 Hz), 148.74 (d, *J*_{CF} = 9.1 Hz), 133.53 (d, *J*_{CF} = 2.3 Hz), 110.38 (d, *J*_{CF} = 2.7 Hz), 100.77 (d, *J*_{CF} = 25.7 Hz), 95.11 (d, *J*_{CF} = 21.1 Hz), 60.95, 39.46, 33.68, 14.31. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₁H₁₄BrFNO₂ [M+H]⁺: 290.01865; found: 290.01876.

Ethyl 3-((4-nitrophenyl)amino)propanoate (**3jm**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-nitroaniline (41 mg, 0.3 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxypropanoate (71 mg, 0.6 mmol) to afford **3jm** (36 mg, 51% yield). Yellow solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 70:30). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 8.09 (d, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 2H), 6.55 (d, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 2H), 4.17 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 3.54 (t, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 2H), 2.64 (t, *J* = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 1.27 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 172.03, 152.86, 138.47, 126.59, 111.33, 61.17, 38.93, 33.64, 14.32. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₁H₁₅N₂O₄ [M+H]⁺: 239.10263; found: 239.10267.

Ethyl 3-((4-cyanophenyl)amino)propanoate (**3jo**)

The compound was synthesized according to the **General procedure** using 4-aminobenzonitrile (35 mg, 0.3 mmol) and ethyl 3-hydroxypropanoate (71 mg, 0.6 mmol) to afford **3jo** (34 mg, 52% yield). Light yellow semi-solid was obtained after column chromatography (SiO₂, Pentane/EtOAc 70:30). **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 7.41 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 6.56 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 4.66 (*br s*, 1H), 4.16 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 3.48 (t, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 2H), 2.61 (t, *J* = 6.0 Hz, 2H), 1.26 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 172.08, 150.90, 133.88, 120.45, 112.42, 99.18, 61.03, 38.72, 33.67, 14.29. **HRMS** (APCI⁺, *m/z*) calculated for C₁₂H₁₅N₂O₂ [M+H]⁺: 219.11280; found: 219.11283.

Ethyl 3-hydroxyhexanoate-3-d (**1b-d1**)

The compound was synthesized according to the literature procedure.¹⁴ **¹H NMR** (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 4.12 (q, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 2.92 (*br s*, 1H), 2.44 (d, *J* = 16.4 Hz, 1H), 2.35 (d, *J* = 16.4 Hz, 1H), 1.50-1.29 (m, 4H), 1.22 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H), 0.88 (t, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 3H). **¹³C NMR** (151 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 173.01, 67.30 (t, *J* = 22.0 Hz), 60.58, 41.27, 38.54, 18.61, 14.13, 13.91.

¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra

Supplementary Figure 17: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3aa.

Supplementary Figure 18: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3ab.

Supplementary Figure 19: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3ac.

Supplementary Figure 20: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3ad.

Supplementary Figure 21: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3ae.

Supplementary Figure 22: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3af.

Supplementary Figure 23: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3ag.

Supplementary Figure 24: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3ah.

Supplementary Figure 25: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3ai.

Supplementary Figure 26: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3aj.

Supplementary Figure 27: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3ak.

Supplementary Figure 28: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3aI.

Supplementary Figure 29: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3am.

Supplementary Figure 30: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3an.

Supplementary Figure 31: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3ao.

Supplementary Figure 32: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3ap.

Supplementary Figure 33: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3aq.

Supplementary Figure 34: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3ar.

Supplementary Figure 35: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3ba.

Supplementary Figure 36: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3bi.

Supplementary Figure 37: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3ca.

Supplementary Figure 38: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3ci.

Supplementary Figure 39: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3da.

Supplementary Figure 40: ^1H and ^{13}C NMR of compound 3di.

Supplementary Figure 41: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3ea.

Supplementary Figure 42: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3ei.

Supplementary Figure 43: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3fa.

Supplementary Figure 44: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3fi.

Supplementary Figure 45: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 4ei.

Supplementary Figure 46: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3ia.

Supplementary Figure 47: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3ia^A.

Supplementary Figure 48: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3ii.

Supplementary Figure 49: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3ik.

Supplementary Figure 50: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3im.

Supplementary Figure 51: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3io.

Supplementary Figure 52: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3ja.

Supplementary Figure 53: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3ja[^].

Supplementary Figure 54: ^1H and ^{13}C NMR of compound 3ji.

Supplementary Figure 55: ^1H and ^{13}C NMR of compound 3jk.

Supplementary Figure 56: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 3jm.

Supplementary Figure 57: ^1H and ^{13}C NMR of compound 3jo.

Supplementary Figure 58: ¹H and ¹³C NMR of compound 1b-d1.

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